

Final report

Bat sounds on Xeno-canto and GBIF

Aanvrager	Stichting Xeno-canto voor Natuurgeluiden (“Xeno-canto”, “XC”)
Partners	Initial phase: Gloriana Chaverri and Marcelo Araya (Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica) Extension 1: Lia Gilmour, Bat Conservation Trust (UK) Extension 2: Panagiotis Georgiakakis, Natural History Museum Crete/University of Crete (Greece)
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1. Abstract

On 31 may 2021 Xeno-canto received word that NLBIF had awarded its project “Bat sounds on Xeno-canto and GBIF” in the 2021 NLBIF call. Two extensions to the project have been granted NLBIF to use part of the grant that was not used in the initially foreseen activities, the first on 13 march 2024, the second on 10 july 2025.

During the project the existing XC infrastructure was extended to accommodate Bat Sounds, and an attempt was made to mobilise the Bat community to share sounds and make them available for education, research, monitoring and protection.

The initial stage of the project was performed in cooperation with Gloriana Chaverri and Marcelo Araya from the Universidad de Costa Rica; the first extension to the project was carried out in cooperation with the Lia Gilmour representing the Bat Conservation Trust in the UK and the second extension together with Panagiotis Georgiakakis from the Natural History Museum of Crete and the University of Crete.

At the time of writing of this report 200 recordists share 6697 recordings of 190 species of Bats on XC. Just over 90% of the recordings have been shared on GBIF as well.

2. Report

2.1 Initial phase

The project aimed to:

- provide a unique and stable infrastructure for an open, worldwide shared (i.e. CC-licensed) collection of bat (Chiroptera) sounds. The sounds and metadata are available openly through a website and an API.
- initiate the shared collection of bat sounds with 1.000+ recordings of 100+ species mostly from the Neotropical region but also from Europe.
- stimulate bat specialists and general naturalists to share their recordings to the database. The expectation is that this will lead to the addition of hundreds or thousands of recordings every year.

The following activities were specified at the start of the project as necessary to achieve a *minimum viable result*.

1. *Addition of the basic taxonomy of Chiroptera (e.g. from Catalogue of Life/ITIS, Mammals Species of the World or Handbook of the Mammals of the World) to the Xeno-canto taxonomic backbone. (ca.1.332 species, based on Catalogue of Life/ITIS).*

We have settled on: Mammal Diversity Database. 2023. Mammal Diversity Database (Version 1.11).

2. *Expand the range of metadata necessary to describe the recordings.*

The metadata specific for bats (and other sound producing groups on XC for that matter) can be found in this document:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1aMLIF97Im-vX-Py-2bRAANpniTByBGIDC8HYPuVuIVs/edit?gid=1370822890#gid=1370822890>

3. *Update the data pipeline used to publish the metadata on GBIF, and activate it so that Xeno-canto's bat sounds are published as a separate dataset on GBIF.*

The Bat data from XC are published on GBIF on this page:

<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/6bd8ad26-218d-4657-8549-c30d69356664>

4. *Adaptation of homepage, statistics, general navigation, species pages, and search screens.*

Presence of Bats on all these pages has been implemented by adding them to a drop-down that allows one to select a single sound-producing group on the site.

5. *Add support for all sound file formats currently used by bat researchers or produced by automatic recording units, if not already supported. This will include support for*

uncompressed or lossless compressed sounds with sample frequencies up to 384kHz and a bit depth of 16bit.

In fact we have restricted the accepted sound file formats to those that represent real-time recordings. Any sampling frequency is allowed, including frequencies above 384kHz.

6. *Update the Xeno-canto API to include bat sounds.*

Results for bats are included in API exports. Queries can be restricted to Bat sounds using the tag **grp:bats**. All search options are explained on <https://xeno-canto.org/help/search>

7. *Add any missing visual representation of sounds that is commonly used for bats or adapt existing ones so they are useful for Bat sounds.*

It turned out everything that was needed was already in place after the implementations mentioned in point 4.

8. *Ready and add at least 1.000 recordings of around 100 species (or roughly 7% of all bat species) to the expanded database.*

The cooperation with the University of Costa Rica led to the upload of about 500 recordings of about 75 species.

The Bat collection on XC went live on 17 may 2023.

2.2 First extension: British Bats

XC was contacted by the Bat Conservation Trust, the UKs main institution for monitoring of its bat populations, in 2024. After agreeing with NLBIF to redirect part of the funds towards mobilising recordings from BCT, a collaboration was set up. This has resulted in a campaign to promote XC among BCT's 5000+ members, and a first set of 394 recordings from the BCT's archives. The collaboration with BCT is continued in the followup NLBIF project on supporting annotated recordings on XC. BCT has committed to upload at least 100 more manually verified recordings from rarer species, making sure all British species are represented and to mobilise 2000 new bat call recordings into XC through their network.

2.3 Second extension: Bats of Crete

Via Leonie Baier, Vincent Kalkman, Burooj Ghani and Dan Stowell at Naturalis and working for the European Mambo project, XC came into contact with Panagiotis Georgiakakis, a bat researcher at the Naturalis History Museum of Crete and the University of Crete. This resulted in an addition of an estimated 2500 recordings to the XC Bat collection, and also in a closer cooperation with these researchers.

2.4 Publicity

In the initial phase the project has been publicised through the XC website, its X account (which is no longer active) and press releases in the Netherlands and Costa Rica. A few relevant links are shown below.

<https://www.naturetoday.com/nl/nl/nature-reports/message/?msg=30944#:~:text=24%2DJUN%2D2023%20%2D%20Xeno.gemaakt%20voor%20het%20menselijk%20oor.>

<https://www.ucr.ac.cr/noticias/2023/6/22/sabias-que-los-murcielagos-emiten-senales-acusticas-estos-curiosos-sonidos-ahora-son-de-acceso-libre.html>

<https://www.nacion.com/ciencia/medio-ambiente/biologos-de-ucr-crean-biblioteca-acustica-con/UEFOVOSSANGHZMLXXQMEGOXOKI/story/>

For the first extension, BCT is now starting to reach out to their network. They promoted the upload to XC at their National Bat Conference in early September 2025, they've created a web page on the BCT website that is due to go live shortly, they've sent out a call for people to upload their recordings in their Bat News newsletter. They've started a social media campaign and post in relevant groups and networks. The campaign will include weekly posts and updates on progress.

For the second extension the Mambo group presented a poster at the 2025 conference of IBAC (International Bioacoustic Society) where they invited Bat researchers to share their recordings on XC. The additions were mentioned on the Bluesky account of XC (<https://bsky.app/profile/xeno-canto.bsky.social>).

3. Conclusion

At the time of writing of this report 200 recordists share 6697 recordings of 190 species of Bats. This fulfills the ambition stated in the original proposal. 6300 recordings have been or will be shared with GBIF making up a significant percentage (slightly less than 20% at the end of 2025) of the Bat recordings there. A large proportion of the recordings has been uploaded by individual Bat aficionados, and by Bat researchers and research groups that were not part of the initial call. XC think the Bat sound collection has found its place in the wider Bat community and will keep growing in years to come.

4. Financial report

The NLBIF grant 2021.018 amounted to EUR 13842,20

Description	number of invoice	Amount (EUR)
Costa Rican recordings, setting up Bats branch on XC	1	1500
Costa Rican recordings 2	2	636,00
Bat Conservation Trust, mobilising bat recordings to XC	3	8317,01
Mobilising Greek recordings	4 (please note that "collection" in the description on the invoice actually means curation/readying of already recorded sounds for XC.	3000
Xeno-canto contributions to: project management, functional specification, adding Bats to XC taxonomy and functionality, GBIF pipeline, update API, uploading sounds for partners	n/a	389,19
Total		13842,20

Partner	hours	EUR (€) excl VAT	EUR incl VAT
NLBIF		11440	13842,20
Xeno-canto, in-kind contribution	40	2600	3146
Universidad de Costa Rica, in-kind contribution	30	1950	2359,50
Total		15.990	19347,90